

SAGER guidelines for Sex and Gender equity in research: 6-item checklist

Please indicate whether you have included the following information in each section of your manuscript.

For more information about the SAGER guidelines, please see:

<https://ease.org.uk/communities/gender-policy-committee/the-sager-guidelines/>

A glossary of terminology is available as an appendix to the guidelines, here:

<https://researchintegrityjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s41073-016-0007-6#appendices>

Recommendations per section of the article		Completed
Title	If only one sex is included in the study, or if the results of the study are to be applied to only one sex or gender, the title should specify the sex of animals or any cells, tissues and other material derived from these and the sex and gender of human participants.	
Abstract	If only one sex is included in the study, or if the results of the study are to be applied to only one sex or gender, the abstract should specify the sex of animals or any cells, tissues and other material derived from these and the sex and gender of human participants.	
Introduction	Authors should report, where relevant, whether sex and/or gender differences may be expected.	
Methods	Authors should report how sex and gender were taken into account in the design of the study, whether they ensured adequate representation of males and females, and justify the reasons for any exclusion of males or females.	
Results	Where appropriate, data should be routinely presented disaggregated by sex and gender. Sex- and gender-based analyses should be reported regardless of positive or negative outcome. In clinical trials, data on withdrawals and dropouts should also be reported disaggregated by sex.	
Discussion	The potential implications of sex and gender on the study results and analyses should be discussed. If a sex and gender analysis was not conducted, the rationale should be given. Authors should further discuss the implications of the lack of such analysis on the interpretation of the results.	

Article title:

Intimate Partner Violence and Emotional Exhaustion: A Female Gender Perspective in the University Environment

Lima, September 2023